

1 SOIL RESPIRATION IN A MIXED TEMPERATE FOREST AND ITS
2 CONTRIBUTION TO TOTAL ECOSYSTEM RESPIRATION

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1 **Summary**

2

3 Soil respiration (SR) was measured within a mixed coniferous-deciduous forest in the
4 Belgian Campine region with an infrared gas analyser in 9 plots, representative for the
5 heterogeneous vegetation in this forest. Selected plots included the two most representative
6 overstorey species (*Pinus sylvestris* L. and *Quercus robur* L.) in combination with the most
7 representative understorey species of the forest. A model that includes temperature and
8 water as the two main controlling variables was fitted to the data. We found large spatial
9 variability in SR among plots, with fluxes under coniferous typically lower than under
10 deciduous overstorey (averaging 4.8 ± 0.4 ton C ha⁻¹ y⁻¹ and 8.8 ± 0.5 ton C ha⁻¹ y⁻¹ under
11 coniferous and deciduous vegetation respectively). Total annual soil carbon (C) emissions
12 were estimated by weighting fluxes from different vegetations according to their relative
13 contribution to the footprint area of the eddy covariance flux measurement. The relative
14 contribution of the two main tree species to the footprint-weighted total SR varied among
15 seasons with the more abundant coniferous overstorey contributing most to total SR during
16 most of the year. Nonetheless, during summer, the contribution of deciduous plots to total
17 SR was disproportionally high because of the more pronounced seasonality of
18 belowground metabolic activity. Net ecosystem CO₂ exchange was measured with eddy
19 covariance, and we used footprint-constrained nighttime fluxes to estimate the total
20 ecosystem respiration (TER). Average total annual SR and TER were 6.1 ± 0.11 ton C ha⁻¹
21 y⁻¹ and 9.1 ± 1.15 ton C ha⁻¹ y⁻¹, respectively. The 95% confidence interval of the ratio of
22 annual SR to annual TER ranged from 0.58 to 0.76, with an average of 0.67. The
23 contribution of SR to TER tended to vary seasonally, with minimum contribution during

1 summer (less than 50% of TER) and maximum contribution during winter (around 94% of
2 TER).

3

4 *Keywords:* coniferous, deciduous, ecosystem respiration, NEE, net ecosystem exchange,
5 seasonal evolution, soil respiration, carbon allocation.

1 **Introduction**

2

3 On a global scale, soil respiration (SR) is the second largest carbon flux between the
4 atmosphere and the terrestrial biosphere (Schlesinger & Andrews 2000). Because soil
5 temperature and soil moisture explain most of the temporal and spatial variation in soil
6 respiration (Raich & Potter 1995, Borken et al. 2002), climate-change induced changes in
7 SR have the potential to substantially alter the role of soil respiration in the global C cycle.
8 Also at the ecosystem scale, SR is the largest respiratory C flux, and the second most
9 important C flux after gross primary productivity (Lavigne et al. 1997, Law et al. 1999,
10 Longdoz et al. 2000, Janssens et al. 2001b, Pilegaard et al. 2001, Lai et al. 2002, Wang et
11 al. 2004).

12 There have been several studies where SR was measured by a chamber-based method and
13 TER by the eddy covariance method. The SR:TER-ratios published in these studies varied
14 from 0.37 in a beech forest in Denmark (Pilegaard et al. 2001) to 1.38 under a
15 Mediterranean deciduous forest in Italy (Janssens et al. 2001a). This wide range suggests
16 firstly, that the contribution of SR may differ from ecosystem to ecosystem, depending on
17 site biomass (Longdoz et al. 2000), vegetation type (Janssens et al. 1999) or age
18 (Buchmann 2000). Secondly, because SR by definition cannot exceed TER, that a number
19 of unresolved methodological issues may have introduced under- or overestimation in both
20 SR and TER estimates (Janssens et al. 2001a). Several intercomparison studies have been
21 carried out to compare chamber-based methods with the eddy covariance method (Anthony
22 et al. 1999, Law et al. 1999, Janssens et al. 2001a, Curtis et al. 2002, Ehman et al. 2002).

1 In general, the eddy covariance method tends to produce lower fluxes than chamber-based
2 methods.

3 For a more complete review of the uncertainties associated with the use of the eddy
4 covariance technique to estimate ecosystem respiration, the reader is referred to Baldocchi
5 (2003). Perhaps the most important issue related to the use of nighttime NEE fluxes to
6 derive TER is the underestimation of nighttime fluxes because of insufficient turbulent
7 mixing in the upper canopy due to stable atmospheric conditions. Typically investigators
8 try to overcome this problem by avoiding data collected during low-turbulent periods. This
9 selection is based on a regression between CO₂ flux density and friction velocity (u^*)
10 (Goulden et al. 1996, Hollinger et al. 1999, Aubinet et al. 2000, Falge et al. 2001, Xu and
11 Baldocchi 2004), and identifying the u^* value above which fluxes become independent of
12 u^* . However, often it is unclear what the most appropriate threshold would be, and
13 sometimes fluxes appear to be correlated with u^* even at high u^* values. In addition to the
14 unreliable fluxes at low turbulence, the horizontal stratification of the atmosphere during
15 stable nighttime conditions may produce large footprints and thus uncouple the eddy
16 covariance measurements from the chamber measurements that are measured closer to the
17 tower.

18 For chamber-based techniques, the critical issue is the large inherent spatial variability
19 (Livingston and Hutchinson 1995, Lund et al. 1999, Davidson et al. 2002). Scaling up from
20 a limited number of chambers to the entire forest may therefore introduce large
21 uncertainties. Moreover, several systematic errors have been reported for chamber systems,
22 such as perturbation of the local pressure, wind and CO₂ concentration gradient (see

1 Davidson et al. 2002 for a review). In general, closed-dynamic chambers such as the one
2 used in this study performs relatively well (Pumpanen et al. 2004).
3 Despite the uncertainties associated with the methods, the comparison of SR and TER may
4 provide valuable information about ecological processes, such as patterns in C allocation
5 to above- and belowground forest compartments. In this study, we compare TER estimates
6 based on foot-print corrected nighttime eddy-covariance measurements with upscaled SR
7 measurements made in 9 different, representative plots within the footprint area. In
8 particular, the aims of this study were 1. to estimate the total annual soil CO₂ flux from a
9 mixed coniferous deciduous temperate forest using a chamber-based technique; 2. to
10 estimate the contribution of SR to TER on an annual and monthly basis; 3. to analyse the
11 contributions of deciduous and coniferous vegetation to soil fluxes in this complex
12 ecosystem.
13

1 **Materials and Methods**

2

3 *Plot description*

4

5 The experimental forest 'De Inslag' is located in Brasschaat, 20 km NE of Antwerp in the
6 Belgian Campine region (51°18' N and 4° 31' E). 'De Inslag' is a level-II observation plot
7 of the European Programme for Intensive Monitoring of Forest Ecosystems (EC regulation
8 No. 3528/86 and UN/ECE), and is managed by the Institute for Forestry and Game
9 Management (Flanders, Belgium). The forest is also part of the Carboeuroflux research
10 network (<http://www.bgc-jena.mpg.de/public/carboeur/>), funded by the European
11 Commission's Fifth Framework Programme.

12 The site has a temperate maritime climate, with long-term mean annual temperature of 9.8
13 °C, and, respectively, 3° C and 18° C as long-term mean temperatures of the coldest and
14 warmest month (Janssens et al. 1999). Mean annual precipitation is 750 mm. However,
15 2001, when this study was performed, was hotter and wetter than the long-term means
16 (mean annual temperature of 10.6 °C and total precipitation of 960 mm). Site topography
17 is almost flat (slope: 0.3%), and the elevation is 16 m. The forest has a moderately wet,
18 sandy soil with a distinct humus and/or iron B-horizon (Baeyens et al. 1993). The soil type
19 is a psammentic haplumbrept (U.S.D.A. classification) or an umbric regosol (F.A.O.
20 classification). The site has poor drainage due to a clay layer at a depth of 1.5 to 2 m. The
21 soil is moist, but rarely saturated, due to the high hydraulic conductivity in the upper layers
22 (sand). Soil water content (SWC) typically fluctuates around field capacity (0.123 m³ m⁻³).
23 However, 2001, the year in which the study was performed, was a relatively wet year and

1 SWC was above field capacity during most of the year (Figure 1). More detailed
2 information on the soil and local climatic conditions can be found in Baeyens et al. (1993),
3 Janssens et al. (1999) and Kowalski et al. (2000).

4

5 *Species contribution to ground cover*

6 This 'urban' mixed forest (150 ha) consisted of 117 patches with a wide variety in species
7 composition. Although several tree species occurred, two species clearly dominated, *i.e.*
8 Scots pine (*Pinus sylvestris* L.; over 80% of the coniferous trees), which covered 50% of
9 the surface area, and pedunculate oak (*Quercus robur* L.; over 80% of the deciduous trees),
10 which covered 35 % of the surface area. Scots pines were all planted in 1929, and tree
11 density at the time of the study was 376 trees ha⁻¹, with a mean tree height of 20.8 m and a
12 mean diameter at breast height (DBH, measured at 1.3 m) of 0.29 m. Pedunculate oaks
13 were planted in 1936, with a tree density of 318 trees ha⁻¹, a mean tree height of 17.2 m
14 and mean DBH of 0.24 m. Black cherry (*Prunus serotina* Ehrh.), rhododendron
15 (*Rhododendron ponticum* L.), grass (*Molinia caerulea* (L.)) and mixtures of endemic
16 broadleaf species (genera *Alnus*, *Carpinus*, *Fagus*, *Corylus* and *Betula*) dominated the
17 understorey vegetation. Based on the most representative overstorey-understorey species
18 compositions named above, four plots with coniferous overstorey and four with deciduous
19 overstorey were selected within a radius of 500 m around a meteorological tower (Table
20 1).

21

1 *Soil respiration measurements*

2 A closed dynamic system (IRGA: CIRAS-1, soil chamber: SRC-1, both PP-Systems,
3 Hitching, UK) was used to measure soil respiration. To mitigate spatial variability, we
4 enlarged the surface area sampled by the chamber by attaching a PVC-rim to the base of
5 the chamber. This modification did not alter the measurements (Janssens et al. 2000). Ten
6 PVC-collars (20-cm diameter, 16 cm height) were installed randomly at each of the nine
7 plots during November 2000. Soil temperature and soil water content were logged
8 continuously in the vicinity of the meteorological tower. For more information about collar
9 design and installation, and on meteorological instrumentation see Curiel Yuste et al
10 (2003).

11

12 Measurements of SR were performed once a month in the nine plots during one year from
13 early January 2001 (2 months after collars were inserted) until the end of December 2001.
14 Two plots (Scots pines without no understorey and pedunculate oaks without understorey)
15 were more intensively monitored (66 measurement dates at each plot). Measurements in
16 the grassland plot were not performed during the coldest months. To get a more accurate
17 estimate, SR was measured twice at each collar, at each sampling campaign and the mean
18 was used in the calculations. SR was pooled over all 10 collars per plot.

19

20 *Soil respiration model*

21 The following equation was fitted to soil respiration measured in each vegetation type:

22

23 $SR = f(T) * f(SWC)$, *equation 1*

1

2 Where SR is the soil respiration, $f(T)$ an exponential function depending on soil
 3 temperature and $f(SWC)$ a function to correct for soil drought when soil water content
 4 (SWC) was below certain threshold and recent rain events did not rewet the soil.

5

6 The function used for the temperature response was an exponential Q_{10} function:

7

$$8 \quad SR = SR_{10} * Q_{10}^{((T-10)/10)} \quad \text{equation 2}$$

9

10 in which SR is the measured soil respiration, SR_{10} is the simulated SR at 10°C, Q_{10} is the
 11 temperature sensitivity of SR (the respiratory flux at one temperature over the flux at a
 12 temperature 10°C lower), and T is the measured soil temperature at 2 cm depth.

13

14 The correction for soil drought was done only when soil moisture was below 0.15 m³ m⁻³
 15 volumetric water content (above this threshold we did not observe drought effects). The
 16 applied moisture response function was:

17

$$18 \quad f(SWC) = a * SWC + b, \quad \text{equation 3}$$

19

20 Where SWC is the soil water content in m³ m⁻³ measured at 25 cm, and a and b are
 21 parameters (Table 2).

22

1 In Curiel Yuste et al. (2003), we reported that under limited SWC conditions rain events
 2 often, but not always, enhanced SR in such a degree that temperature control over SR was
 3 restored. Hence, we analyzed the data to see when rain events had the capacity to affect
 4 SR. Quantification of the rewetting capacity of rain events was done using a rewetting
 5 index (I_w):

6

$$7 \quad I_w = a + \text{Log} [\text{sqrt}(R)/(VPD_a * (t)^2)] \quad \text{equation 4}$$

8

9 Where a is a constant (2.5), R represents the amount of precipitation during the last rainfall
 10 event (mm), t is the time since the last rain event (h), and VPD_a the mean vapour pressure
 11 deficit of the atmosphere at 1.5 m above the forest floor averaged over the last 24 h (kPa)
 12 . Thus I_w was intended to be a rough representation of the rewetting intensity in the
 13 uppermost soil layers where no moisture sensors were installed. When I_w was above 0.3,
 14 temperature only controlled the temporal variation in SR, even when soil moisture was
 15 below $0.15 \text{ m}^3 \text{ m}^{-3}$ volumetric water content. More information about this index, the
 16 equation design and the environmental factors used can be found in Curiel Yuste et al.
 17 (2003).

18

19 It is widely accepted that Q_{10} for most biochemical processes is close to 2, while SR_{10}
 20 fluctuates seasonally due to the continuous changes in root- and microbial biomass and
 21 metabolic activity. Under this assumption, the Q_{10} value in *equation 2* was fixed at 2 and
 22 only SR_{10} was allowed to fluctuate seasonally. SR_{10} was calculated as follows:

23

1 $SR_{10} = (\text{measured SR} / (2^{(T-10)/10}) / f(\text{SWC}))$ *equation 5*

2

3 This equation generated an estimate of SR_{10} at each sampling date. To estimate SR in
4 between the measurements dates, we interpolated SR_{10} by fitting the following equation to
5 the available SR_{10} estimates:

6

7 $SR_{10} = a + b * e^{(-e^{(-z)-z} + 1)}$ *equation 6*

8 $z = (\text{DOY} - c) / d$ *equation 7*

9

10 where SR_{10} is the basal soil respiration at 10 degrees calculated with *equation 4*; a , b , c , d
11 and z are parameters and DOY the day of the year when the measurement was taken. This
12 function was chosen because the shape resembled the seasonal evolution of SR_{10} , with a
13 conspicuous peak during the summer. This peak is asymmetric because SR_{10} increases
14 sharply at the onset of spring and decreases gradually at the end of summer. Figure 2 shows
15 the shape of the function and summarises the role of each of the four parameters. Parameter
16 b controls the amplitude of the seasonal change in SR_{10} (range on Y-axis), parameter c the
17 width or duration of the peak (range on X-axis), parameter a the intercept on the Y-axis
18 and parameter d the date at which SR_{10} starts to increase in spring. This function was fitted
19 to the seasonal record of calculated SR_{10} at each individual plot (Figure 3, Table 2).

20

21

1 *Eddy covariance measurements and ecosystem respiration model*

2

3 To calculate the total ecosystem respiration (TER) we used half-hourly mean nighttime
 4 fluxes (F_n) measured with the eddy covariance technique from a scaffold tower at a height
 5 of 41 m. For more information about data collection, instruments, instrument calibration
 6 and quality control methodology, we refer the reader to Carrara et al (2003).

7

8 The calculation of eddy covariance fluxes and the processes of data corrections followed
 9 the guidelines of the standard EUROFLUX methodology (Aubinet et al., 2000). We
 10 assumed stationarity and horizontal homogeneity of turbulence, and negligible horizontal
 11 flux divergence and molecular diffusion. Because the terrain was flat and because an
 12 accurate estimate of the advection term was impossible to obtain, we neglected this term
 13 in this study. Therefore the nighttime ecosystem respiration was deduced from the
 14 nighttime eddy flux and the storage term as follows:

15

$$16 \quad \text{TER} = F_n + F_{\Delta S} \quad \text{equation 8}$$

17

18 Where TER is the half-hourly average nighttime ecosystem respiration, $F_n = \overline{w'c'}$ is the
 19 half-hourly average eddy covariance flux and $F_{\Delta S}$ is the CO₂ storage term in the air layer
 20 below the eddy measurement height.

21

22 However, because of the limited dimensions of the study site and the height at which the
 23 eddy system was installed, a high proportion of the nighttime F_n was believed to originate

1 from outside the forest boundaries (Nagy et al. submitted). In order to eliminate fluxes
 2 originating from outside of the forest, it was necessary to analyse the footprint area. The
 3 footprint of the eddy covariance flux measurements was calculated based on the work of
 4 Rebmann et al. (2003). In that study the footprint estimate depended on the quality
 5 assessment of turbulent flux data. Fluxes were separated in 3 data classes: stable conditions
 6 ($\xi > 0.0625$), neutral conditions ($-0.0625 > \xi > 0.0625$) and unstable conditions ($-0.0625 >$
 7 ξ). The stability parameter ξ was calculated as:

$$\xi = \frac{(z_m - d)}{L} \quad \text{equation 9}$$

8
 9
 10 Where z_m is the observation height, d is the zero plane displacement and L is the Obukhov-
 11 length. The majority of the fluxes obtained under stable conditions originated outside of
 12 the forest area, while fluxes during unstable conditions clearly originated from within the
 13 forest. Hence, we removed a large portion of the data following the procedure given below.

14
 15 The surroundings around the flux tower were divided into wind sectors of about 30° each
 16 and we assumed that fluxes at higher ξ originated from a longer distance. Thus different ξ
 17 thresholds were applied for each sector, according to the flux footprint and available fetch
 18 in that direction (-0.0625 where fetch was relatively short, 0 where fetch was sufficiently
 19 large). Data obtained during stable conditions were rejected in every wind sector. Also
 20 some sectors were rejected entirely, because of too short fetch or undesired vegetation type
 21 (e.g. grassland or tree nursery) within the fetch. When the matrix of this footprint was
 22 compared to the forest map, the result suggested that 91 % of the flux data were found to

1 originate from the investigated site in the case of neutral conditions and 97 % in the case
2 of unstable conditions Thus, we assured that 95% of the flux dataset corresponded to the
3 forest ecosystem and was not affected by fluxes from outside of the forest. For more
4 information about methodology of footprint analyses and data selection see Nagy et al.
5 (submitted).

6

7 A Q_{10} function was then fitted to the data withheld after this selection procedure (Figure
8 4a) using also soil temperature (2 cm depth in mineral soil) as reference temperature. Using
9 a similar approach as described above, we derived a seasonal pattern in SR_{10} . To reduce
10 the large scatter of eddy covariance data, measurements were averaged on a weekly basis,
11 we then fitted *equation 6* to the weekly TER_{10} data (Figure 4b). Unlike the soil respiration
12 data, no rewetting effect was found in the nighttime NEE data, which was probably due to
13 the inherent scatter of eddy covariance data, together with a lack of data during the driest
14 period. Therefore the shape of the model for TER was reduced to:

15

$$16 \quad TER = f(T) * f(SWC) \quad \text{equation 10}$$

17

18 Where TER is the measured nighttime NEE as explained above, and $f(T)$ and $f(SWC)$ were
19 similar to those applied for SR (see Table 2 for parameters values and statistics).

20

21 *Scaling up in time and space*

22

1 Because of the large heterogeneity in the forest, it was practically impossible to measure
2 SR in all combinations of overstorey-understorey species. Therefore, two assumptions had
3 to be made:

4 1. Since Scots pine and pedunculate oak occupied 80% of the land covered by coniferous
5 and deciduous trees, respectively (de Pury & Ceulemans 1997), we assumed those two
6 species as being representative of the entire overstorey vegetation of the forest (except, of
7 course, for the grassland).

8 2. Since it would be impossible to account for all overstorey-understorey combinations that
9 occur in the forest, we assumed the 4 most common overstorey-understorey combinations
10 of both oak and pine as being representative of the heterogeneity of the vegetation in this
11 forest (Table 1).

12 To compare SR with the total ecosystem respiration (TER), flux rates were also weighted
13 according to the relative contribution of each vegetation type to ground cover within the
14 area measured by the eddy covariance technique. We calculated the footprint-weighted
15 total ecosystem SR by weighting the SR in different vegetation types with the relative
16 occurrence of this vegetation type in the footprint area (Table 1). For more information
17 about the relative contribution of different vegetation types in the footprint area see Nagy
18 et al. (submitted).

19 Both the SR and TER models were applied on a half-hourly basis and subsequently
20 integrated to obtain the annual C fluxes ($\text{ton C ha}^{-1} \text{ yr}^{-1}$) for each plot (Table 1).

21

22 *Statistical treatment and error computation*

23

1 A non-linear least squares fitter (ORIGIN version 5.0; Northampton, MA USA) was used to
2 determine the exponential fittings of SR_{10} against DOY and of normalized fluxes against
3 SWC.

4 The non-linear least squares fitter estimated the standard error for parameters a and b of
5 *equation 6* with a 95% confidence interval (Table 2). Uncertainties in annual and
6 seasonal fluxes were then estimated by propagation of the errors of parameters a and b .

7

1 **Results and discussion**

2

3 *Spatial and temporal variability of fluxes during 2001*

4

5 Large spatial and temporal variability in SR was found within and among plots (Figure 5).
6 Soil fluxes varied from $0.3 \mu\text{mol m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$ during winter under pines to $5.6 \mu\text{mol m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$ in
7 summer under oak. In general, fluxes were very similar during winter in both the
8 coniferous- and deciduous-dominated plots, but during the growing season, plots
9 dominated by deciduous overstorey showed a larger increase in SR. This larger seasonality
10 in deciduous plots was reflected in the higher values of parameter b in *equation 6* (Table
11 2). Under both pine and oak, plots with deciduous understorey typically showed higher
12 values of *parameter b* than plots without or with evergreen understorey, emphasising the
13 role of deciduousness in the differences in SR. In Curiel Yuste et al. (2004), we
14 hypothesised that the observed differences in seasonality of SR were caused by the
15 differences in fine root phenology between coniferous and deciduous species, as had been
16 observed in other studies (Lyr and Hoffmann 1967, Steele et al. 1997, Coleman et al. 2000).
17 However, a recent study carried out in this forest showed that fine root production was
18 surprisingly more seasonal in a coniferous-dominated plot than in a deciduous-dominated
19 plot, which appears to refute the former hypothesis (Konôpka et al. 2004). However, there
20 is a difference between root biomass and root activity. Root respiration might be affected
21 by temperature, soil moisture, nitrogen availability or substrate supply to the roots
22 (Pregitzer et al. 2000), parameters that change seasonally and perhaps affect differently
23 fine root respiration of oaks and pines. However, no assessment of seasonal changes in root

1 respiration was done in this study. In addition to potential differences in root respiration
2 due to different C allocation to roots, we also observed 6 times higher extramatrical
3 ectomycorrhizal (ECM) hyphal length under oak than under pine (De Clerck 2004). Thus,
4 part of the larger seasonal changes in SR in the oaks may originate from differences in
5 ECM activity.

6

7 In all vegetation types, the proportion of variation (R^2) explained by the empirical model
8 was high, varying from 0.78 to 0.98 (Table 1). Despite the fact that the model was originally
9 developed for a Scots pine stand (Curiel Yuste et al. 2003), it performed rather well in all
10 vegetation types. The footprint-weighted total SR ranged from $0.6 \mu\text{mol m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$ in winter
11 to $4 \mu\text{mol m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$ in summer (Figure 6b).

12

13 As with soil fluxes, there was large seasonal variability in total ecosystem respiration with
14 weekly mean nighttime fluxes typically around $1 \mu\text{mol m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$ during winter and around 5
15 $\mu\text{mol m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$ in late summer (Figure 4a). Unfortunately, due to the stringent quality control,
16 which rejected a large proportion of the nighttime eddy fluxes, and to instrument failures,
17 the total number of available data was low, especially in mid-winter and mid-summer
18 (Figure 4a). The empirical model explained 73% of the variation in weekly TER_{10} (Figure
19 4b), which was high compared with other FLUXNET sites (Falge et al. 2001). Due to the
20 inherent scatter of eddy covariance data, the model only explained 45% of the variation in
21 half-hourly TER_{10} values (Table 1). Modeled ecosystem respiration ranged from $0.6 \mu\text{mol}$
22 $\text{m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$ in winter to more than $8 \mu\text{mol m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$ in late summer (Figure 6b).

23 *Annual estimates of SR*

1

2 Total annual SR in the different vegetations ranged between 4.1 and 13.6 ton C ha⁻¹ y⁻¹
3 (Table 1). The forest-weighted annual C flux from the soil was 6.1 ± 0.8 ton C ha⁻¹. This
4 was within the ranges of SR reported by Raich and Schlesinger (1992) for temperate mixed
5 forests (4.7-7.3 ton C ha⁻¹ y⁻¹), and by Janssens et al. (2001b) for European forest (3.8 – 8.5
6 ton of C ha⁻¹ y⁻¹).

7

8 Annual SR in the grassland plot (13.5 ± 2.0 ton C ha⁻¹ y⁻¹) was above the range reported
9 for grassland in the review by Raich and Schlesinger (1.3-8.3 ton C ha⁻¹ y⁻¹). Perhaps this
10 difference was an artefact because no measurements were taken at this plot during the
11 coldest periods. However, the contribution of grassland ecosystems to total forest SR and
12 hence to TER was almost negligible (Table 1) and therefore not really important in the
13 scaling up to the forest level.

14

15 We observed large differences in total SR between plots with deciduous overstorey
16 (weighted average: 8.8 ± 2.2 ton C ha⁻¹ y⁻¹) and plots with coniferous overstorey (weighted
17 average: 4.8 ± 0.7 ton C ha⁻¹ y⁻¹). Differences in SR between deciduous broadleaf and
18 evergreen coniferous stands, in the absence of differences in temperature, precipitation and
19 soil moisture, have previously been observed (Janssens et al. 1999, Longdoz et al. 2000,
20 Borken et al. 2002). Detailed investigation of the carbon budget in one of the pine and one
21 of the oak stands indicated that, despite the similar age and total litter inputs, the soil C
22 pool in the pine stand was twice that in the oak stand. It is therefore likely that due to the
23 more refractory and acidifying nature of conifer litter (Coley et al. 1985, Van Cleve 1974,

1 Heal et al. 1981, Lockaby et al. 1995, Hobbie 1996, 2000, Kavvadias et al. 2001, Schnitzer
2 and Kahn 1979), decomposition processes were much slower under pine-dominated plots
3 than under oak-dominated plots and that the sites have not reached a new equilibrium yet,
4 *i.e.* soils under pine are still accumulating C.

5

6 There was large seasonal variation in the contributions of deciduous and coniferous plots
7 to total forest SR (Figure 7). Although conifers dominated the vegetation, the contribution
8 of deciduous vegetation to total SR was disproportionally high during the warmest months
9 (Figure 7). The larger seasonal changes in SR under deciduous overstorey may explain this
10 pattern. As explained above, these changes in the contribution to SR of each vegetation
11 type could not be explained by differences in fine root biomass and production as explained
12 above, but were likely attributable to larger changes in specific root and/or ectomycorrhizal
13 activity in oak than in pine.

14

15 *Contribution of SR to TER*

16

17 Total ecosystem respiration estimated from the nighttime eddy covariance fluxes was 9.1
18 ± 1.15 ton of C $\text{ha}^{-1} \text{y}^{-1}$ (Table 1). Therefore, SR contributed for 67 % to TER, with a 95%
19 confidence interval as wide as 58.4 to 75.5 %. The stability parameter ξ allowed us to
20 exclude data influenced by non-forest area under the poor mixing conditions of stable
21 nights, which is one the major problem with nighttime eddy covariance fluxes (see
22 Baldocchi 2003). However, the limited data availability after this quality assessment may
23 have introduced some uncertainty when fitting the model, especially during summer.

1

2 Besides these errors associated with the eddy covariance technique, chamber-based
3 methods are also uncertain mainly because of the spatial scaling (1 m² measured per
4 500,000 m²). However, the 9 different overstorey/understorey combinations used in this
5 study covered most of the spatial heterogeneity in vegetation. Moreover, in this study, 10
6 collars were sampled at each sampling day in each of the 9 study sites, which approached
7 the practical limits of portable SR systems. Davidson et al. (2002) recommended 6-8 flux
8 measurements with chambers covering a similar area (300 cm²) to integrate the spatial
9 variability within relatively homogeneous sites. Therefore the design of this study tried to
10 avoid as much as practically possible the inherent spatial variability of SR within and
11 among homogeneous vegetation types. Nonetheless, there are several other sources of error
12 that might not have been accounted in this study. For example, it is possible that SR
13 measurements were underestimated because our soil collars did not contain slash remaining
14 after a thinning (Carrara et al. 2003), or because closed dynamic systems may
15 underestimate SR fluxes due to alteration of the CO₂ concentration gradient (Nay et al.
16 1994, Livingston & Hutchinson 1995, Healy et al. 1996). Our system underestimated
17 fluxes on coarse sand by 14% (Pumpanen et al. 2004), and may therefore have
18 underestimated fluxes slightly at the loamy-sandy soil of the study site. On the other hand,
19 the more favourable microclimate (less wind and less desiccation) and the trapping of litter
20 within the permanent collars may also have resulted in overestimation of SR during the
21 warmest periods. Unfortunately, we couldn't account for these systematic errors.

22

1 As in most assessments of the contribution of SR to TER (Lavigne et al. 1997, Law et al.
2 1999, Longdoz et al. 2000, Janssens et al. 2001b, Lai et al. 2002, Wang et al. 2004), it was
3 clear that SR was the main respiratory carbon flux within the ecosystem. Although the
4 large uncertainties made the seasonal differences in the contribution of SR to TER not
5 statistically significant, the contribution of SR to TER did show a seasonal trend with
6 maximal contribution in winter and minimal contribution during the period of leaf growth
7 (Figure 6a and 6b). The extremely large contribution of SR to TER during winter (around
8 94% of TER; Figure 6a) supported previously reported trends (Lai et al. 2002, Wang et al.
9 2004). Although the very large uncertainty does not justify any conclusions, higher
10 contribution of SR to TER were expected during winter. This was because winter air
11 temperatures were frequently below zero°C during this period (Figure 1b), and foliage
12 biomass was strongly reduced. Thus, respiration of aboveground plant parts was probably
13 very low in winter. In contrast, soils remained above zero °C (Fig 1b), with significant
14 respiration (Figure 5). This could explain the higher relative importance of SR during
15 winter and why the relative contribution of soils to TER declined with increasing air
16 temperatures.

17

18 The observed decrease in the contribution of SR to TER in spring coincides with the large
19 increase in vegetation area index (VAI) in both oak- and pine-dominated stands (Gond et
20 al. 2000, Konôpka et al. *in press*). It is therefore likely that the decrease in the contribution
21 of SR to TER during late spring-early summer was caused by the combination of reduced
22 root growth during periods of rapid shoot growth (Eissenstat & Van Rees 1994), and high
23 foliar construction respiration costs. Indeed, during this period of rapid increase in VAI, no

1 root growth was observed in both oak and pine (Konôpka et al. *in press*). In contrast, the
2 increase in the contribution of SR to TER observed in summer coincided with the period
3 of maximal fine root production in oak and pine (Konôpka et al. *in press*). In fall and early
4 winter, the period of maximum fine litter production, the contribution of SR to TER
5 averaged around 70%, slightly above the mean annual contribution. In this period of the
6 year the increase in litter inputs coincided with the decrease in VAI (Curiel Yuste et al.
7 submitted, Konôpka et al. *in press*). Fresh material thus becomes available for
8 decomposition, probably enhancing the heterotrophic respiration and resulting in higher
9 SR rates than in spring at similar temperatures (Curiel Yuste et al. submitted). Microbes
10 preferably use the short-lived fractions of SOM as an energy source (Parton et al. 1987,
11 Trumbore et al. 1990, Schimel et al. 1994) and therefore, the fresh litter inputs during late
12 summer and fall were likely to enhance microbial activity during the following months.
13 This may partially explain the relatively high contribution of SR to TER during fall and
14 early winter.

15

16 **Conclusions**

17

18 This study confirms the important role of SR in forest ecosystem C budgets, but also
19 suggest that the contribution of SR to TER is likely to vary seasonally. We hypothesize
20 that the observed seasonal changes in the contribution of SR to TER were due to an
21 antagonistic growth pattern of shoots and roots due to seasonal changes in C allocation, to
22 the larger seasonal changes in foliar biomass than in root biomass and to the differences in
23 soil and air temperature. We further report that soil respiration per unit area was

1 significantly larger under deciduous than under coniferous overstorey. Future studies are
2 needed to support or refute the suggested hypotheses to explain these observations.

3

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14

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24

1 **Figure Captions**

2 **Figure 1.** a) Annual time series of daily mean soil water content at 25 cm in the mineral
3 soil and daily total precipitation. Horizontal line represents the water holding capacity
4 value ($0.123 \text{ m}^3 \text{ m}^{-3}$) b) Annual time series of daily mean soil temperature at 2 cm in the
5 mineral soil and daily mean atmospheric temperature.

6 **Figure 2.** Schematic representation of the behaviour of *equations 6 and 7* (see text) in
7 response to changes in parameters *a, b, c* and *d*. Each graph shows the temporal evolution
8 of basal respiration throughout the year.

9 **Figure 3.** Seasonal evolution of basal soil respiration at 10°C (SR_{10}) calculated for each of
10 the nine study plots and the fitted function to simulate the seasonal changes in SR_{10} (solid
11 line). The dotted lines represent the 95% confidence interval of the model derived by
12 propagation of the errors in parameters *a* and *b* of *equation 6* (see text).

13 **Figure 4.** a) Annual time series of quality-checked nighttime eddy covariance NEE
14 measurements b) Seasonal evolution of weekly average basal ecosystem respiration at 10°C
15 (TER_{10}) calculated with equation 6 (solid squares; see text for information). The number
16 of measurements used to calculate the weekly average TER_{10} (open triangles) and the fitted
17 function (solid line) are also given. The dotted lines represent the 95% confidence interval
18 of the model derived by propagation of the errors in parameters *a* and *b* of equation 6 (see
19 text). Vertical bars represent the standard deviation around the mean weekly TER_{10} .

20 **Figure 5.** Seasonal evolution of soil respiration (SR) in each of the nine plots (see caption
21 in Table 1). Error bars on SR represent the standard deviation of the mean.

22 **Figure 6.** a) Mean monthly forest soil respiration as a percentage of total ecosystem
23 respiration. Up triangles represent period with no eddy covariance data, and open circles

1 periods when eddy covariance data was available. Error bars represent the 95% confidence
2 interval calculated by propagating the standard errors of parameters a and b of *equation 6*.
3 b) Modelled half-hourly total ecosystem respiration (TER) (dotted line), 95% confidence
4 interval (CI) modelled half-hourly ecosystem respiration (grey area) and modelled half-
5 hourly soil respiration (SR) (solid line) as a function of time during 2001.

6 **Figure 7.** Mean monthly contribution to soil respiration (SR) of plots dominated by
7 coniferous overstorey (open circles) and plots dominated by deciduous overstorey (solid
8 squares). Error bars represent the 95% confidence interval calculated by propagating the
9 standard errors of parameters a and b of *equation 6*.

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1 **Figure 1**

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1 **Figure 2**

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1 **Figure 3**

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1 **Figure 4**

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1 **Figure 5**

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1 **Figure 6**

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1 **Figure 7**

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Table 1. Percentage of total land surface covered by each of the vegetation types (% land); total area occupied by each vegetation type (H) and, area of the studied plots (A), both in hectares; percentage of projected ground area covered by understorey vegetation at each plot (% Und.); distance of each plot to the meteorological tower (m); number of measurements carried out during 2001 at each plot (N); coefficient of determination (R^2) and p-value of the non-linear regression; and soil respiration (SR) calculated with the empirical model ($\text{ton C h}^{-1} \text{ yr}^{-1}$). Results of the empirical TER model are also given. pine = Scots pine overstorey without understorey ; pine+rhodo = Scots pine overstorey and understorey dominated by *Rhododendron ponticum*; pine+grass = Scots pine overstorey and understorey dominated by *Molinia careulea*; pine+prunus = Scots pine overstorey and understorey dominated by *Prunus serotina*; oak = pedunculate oak overstorey without understorey; oak+end. sp. = pedunculate oak overstorey and understorey dominated by deciduous species, e.g. *Fagus sylvatica.*, *Sorbus aucuparia*; oak+rhodo = pedunculate oak overstorey and understorey dominated by *Rhododendron ponticum*; oak + prunus = pedunculate oak overstorey, understorey dominated by *Prunus serotina*; and grassland = grassland with endemic gramineae species.

Plot	% land	H	A	% Und	m	N	R^2	p-value	SR
oak	15.4	10.98	1.9	-	450	66	0.96	<0.0001	8.4 ± 0.01
oak + Prunus	8.1	4.19	0.5	60	450	12	0.95	<0.0001	9.7 ± 0.6
oak + Rhodo	2.0	7.44	0.5	60	450	12	0.98	<0.0001	9.1 ± 0.05
oak + end. sp.	2.2	18.48	1.7	50	350	12	0.92	<0.0001	7.5 ± 0.45
pine	20.9	22.57	1.4	-	50	67	0.93	<0.0001	4.1 ± 0.002
pine + Prunus	32.1	36.39	0.8	60	480	12	0.97	<0.0001	5.1 ± 0.04
pine + Rhodo	4.5	3.93	0.3	70	400	12	0.91	<0.0001	5.7 ± 0.006
pine + Molinia	11.5	13.43	0.3	80	450	12	0.94	<0.0001	5.1 ± 0.03
grassland	3.2	15.15	0.6	-	200	7	0.78	0.00947	13.6 ± 1.35
	100.00%	132.56							
SR (weighted average)			-	-	-	-	-	-	6.1 ± 0.11
TER	-	-	-	-	-	4114	0.45	<0.0001	9.1 ± 1.15

Table 2. Values of parameters a , b , c and d from *equation 5* and *equation 6* (see text for information) for both SR_{10} in each plot and TER_{10} . Coefficient of determination (R^2) and p-value of the fit are also presented. Values of parameters f and g of *equation 3* (see text for information) are also given for both soil respiration in each plot and ecosystem respiration.

Plot	SR ₁₀ /TER ₁₀ function						SWC function	
	a	b	c	d	R ²	p-value	f	g
oak	0.9 (0.04)	2.5 (0.12)	220	59	0.92	<0.0001	8.46	-0.32
oak + Prunus	1.45 (0.37)	3.4 (0.81)	195	33	0.89	<0.0001	7.29	-0.18
oak + Rhodo	1.4 (0.18)	1.6 (0.20)	234	70	0.94	<0.0001	2.8	0.57
oak + end. sp.	0.8 (0.22)	2.5 (0.67)	200	50	0.95	<0.0001	8.46	-0.32
pine	0.7 (0.04)	0.7 (0.03)	200	80	0.67	<0.0001	5.2	-0.05
pine + Prunus	0.9 (0.17)	0.9 (0.18)	230	70	0.86	<0.0001	5.2	-0.05
pine + Rhodo	1.2 (0.11)	0.7 (0.06)	240	30	0.73	0.00086	6.99	-0.06
pine + Molinia	0.8 (0.15)	0.9 (0.16)	220	65	0.65	0.0017	6.99	-0.06
grassland	1.1 (0.67)	1.8 (1.10)	150	100	0.59	0.04328	8.46	-0.32
TER	1.0 (0.48)	2.9 (1.05)	192	69	0.67	<0.0001	9.12	-0.47